

Articulating the agenda to manage the increase in neonatal sepsis: The Experiences of healthcare providers at Mbuya Nehanda Maternity Hospital (MNMH) NICU in Harare, Zimbabwe

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Abstract:

Introduction: Maternal and child health are high priorities for international development yet the annual mortality rate per 1 000 live births from neonatal sepsis and other neonatal infections in Zimbabwe has increased by 11.6% since 1990, an average of 0.5% a year (Murray,2016). Zimbabwe's neonatal mortality rate is 24 deaths per 1,000 live births (UNICEF,2015). Successful intervention to reduce neonatal sepsis could be through simple interventions compliance to infection prevention and control guidelines (Newton and Berkley,2009). The study sought to determine the prevalence of neonatal sepsis, establish the factors contributing to the increase in neonatal sepsis and evaluate the practices on IPC by healthcare providers in MNMH NICU

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted at MNMH NICU on 100 neonates who were admitted from June-August 2016.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data.

Results:

- There were 22 incubators but only 10 were functional leaving two or three babies sharing an incubator
- Klebsiella was isolated from the mechanical ventilators.
- Hand swabs revealed presence of pseudomonas
- No filters for suction machines posing high risk of back flow of secretions.
- Shortage of resources such as soap, paper towels and disinfectants
- guidelines is key in prevention of cross infection and it was given as a key recommendation.
- Non-compliance to IPC guidelines by healthcare providers
- Sixty percent of the neonates died of neonatal sepsis.

Conclusion/Recommendation: Presentation of findings to NICU staff and the hospital management team led to improvement of IPC practices. Strategies implemented included decongesting of the unit, improving availability of equipment and sundries and conducting refresher courses for healthcare providers. It is therefore concluded that adherence to IPC guidelines is key in prevention of cross infection and it was given as a key recommendation.

Keywords:

Neonatal sepsis,neonatal infections,neonatal mortality,prevalence,neonate

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Associations among menopausal status, menopausal symptoms and depressive symptoms in midlife women

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Abstract:

Objectives: To determine the associations among menopausal status, menopausal symptoms and depressive symptoms in Chinese midlife women. **Methods:** A secondary analysis involved 3199 women aged 40-55 years was performed based on data from the Women's Health Needs Survey 2018 in Hunan Province, Central South of China. The depressive symptoms were determined using the 9-item Patient Health

Questionnaire. The menopausal symptoms were assessed using the Kupperman Menopausal Index. Demographic characteristics and menopausal status were measured using self-administered questionnaires.

Results: The prevalence of depressive symptoms was 19.3%. The three most common menopausal symptoms were insomnia (48.0%), fatigue (42.7%) and mood swing (39.8%). The increase in depressive symptoms was significantly associated with menopausal status and menopausal symptoms. After controlling for demographic variables, multivariate logistic regression showed perimenopause[odds ratio(OR)=1.14 , 95% confidence interval(95%CI) =(1.12-1.86)], postmenopause [OR =1.52, 95%CI=(1.09-2.11)] and four menopausal symptoms including mood swing[OR= 1.32, 95%CI=(1.03-1.70)], depressive mood[OR= 2.28, 95%CI=(1.79-2.91)], palpitations[OR= 1.37, 95%CI=(1.06-1.77)], urinary tract infection [OR= 1.49, 95%CI=(1.16-1.92)] were associated with depressive symptoms.

Conclusions: Independent of demographic variables, perimenopause and postmenopause and four menopausal symptoms (mood swing, depressive mood, palpitations, urinary tract infection) increase the risk of depressive symptoms.

Keywords:

Menopausal status; menopausal symptoms; depressive symptoms; midlife women; China; a secondary analysis

Sexual Health care delivery to Iranian women: A cross-sectional study in Iran

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Abstract:

Women constitute about half of the Iranian population. Sexual behaviour is one of the most important elements in their lives. Identifying the elements associated with sexual behaviours seems necessary in order to draw a thorough picture of Iranian women's sexuality. To elicit information from Iranian women at their reproductive ages on sexual behaviours related to their elements including sexual capacity, sexual motivation, performance and sexual scripts. Study participants involved 295 women at reproductive age from five different cities. Women completed a national self-reporting questionnaire on elements related to sexual behaviours. The elements included sexual capacity, sexual motivation, sexual performance, and sexual script. Pearson's correlation variance analysis and multi-linear regression were used to analyze data. Significant positive correlation was found between the sexual capacity, motivation, performance, and sexual script ($p < 0.001$). Linear regression showed that the effective variable on the sexual performance were women's ages ($p = 0.02$), and tertiary education ($p = 0.05$). A significant association was found between age and sexual motivation score, too. A significant relation was observed between the history of pregnancy and level of education with a positive response to sexual script questions. Identifying the elements of sexual behaviours would help women understand their sexual behaviours and related influencing factors. Therefore, enrichment of women's sexuality is needed; also a well-planned educational program is a need for women to understand their sexuality-related potentials.

Keywords:

Sexual behavior, Iranian women, Reproductive age.

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Primary sexual Health assessment and service delivery for women with spinal cord injury

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Abstract:

Spinal cord injury affects different aspects of life, including the sexual life of the affected person. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the Plissit model on the sexual function and adjustment of women with spinal cord injury. This is a randomized clinical trial that was performed on 44 women with spinal cord injury. The sample was randomized into two groups of intervention and control (22 in each group) using random blocks. The intervention group received the Plissit sexual counseling in three sessions weekly for 45 minutes, and the control group received the routine consultation of the center. The data were collected using the female sexual function index (FSFI) and sexual adjustment questionnaire (SAQ). The sexual function and adjustment score of these individuals were measured before the intervention, four weeks and eight weeks later. ANOVA test with repeated measures was used to compare the sexual function and adjustment at different times. The results of the data analysis showed that the mean score of sexual function of the intervention group was 15.99 ± 8.48 before the intervention, 21.57 ± 5.58 four weeks later and 21.75 ± 4.3 eight weeks after the intervention, which was significantly increased ($p = 0.00$). The mean score of female sexual adjustment was 32.9 ± 3.2 in the intervention group, 37.95 ± 3.04 four weeks after the intervention and 38.6 ± 2.17 eight weeks after the intervention ($p = 0.00$) indicating that the Plissit model has improved the sexual function and adjustment of women with spinal cord injury. Regarding the effectiveness of sexual counseling based on the Plissit model in improving sexual function and sexual adjustment in women with spinal cord injury, the results of this study can be used to promote the sexual health of these women.

Keywords:

Sexual function, Sexual Adjustment, Plissit Model, Spinal Cord Injury

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